

ISic1579

I.Sicily inscription 1579

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐπὶ ἱερέως το[---]
2. τῶν Μουσῶν
3. Ἀπολλωνίου
4. Συρακοσί[ου]
5. Νύμφωνος υ[ἰοῦ]
6. Συρακοσίου
- 6a. (vac.unknown)
7. ἐπειδὴ Σῶσις Ἄρισ[---]
8. σιος πρόξενος τ[ῶν]
9. κ,ρ,ι,γῶν τῶν περ[ὶ]
10. [τὰς Μούσα]ς κα[---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493913

EDCS 41300089

PHI 175704

PHI 331242

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 34.0974

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1971.0760

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1964.0622

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 106

Orsi, P. 1900. Frammenti epigrafici sicelioti. *Rivista di storia antica*. 5: 39-66. At 62

Manganaro, G. 1963. Nuove ricerche di epigrafia siceliota. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 16: 51-64. At 59

Moretti, L. 1963. I technitai di Siracusa. *Rivista di Filologia e di Istruzione Classica*. 91: 38-45. At 40

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1966. Quattro iscrizioni greche del museo di Palermo. *Kokalos*. 12: 200-206. At 204-206 ph

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